

Comparative Analysis of Compressive Sensing Reconstruction Algorithms for ECG Signals

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Abstract—In the era of the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), modern healthcare devices are overwhelmed with vast amount of data. Managing this data volume requires enhanced data processing capabilities, increased storage capacity, higher transmission bandwidth, and consequently, greater power consumption, especially in sensing applications. Compressive Sensing (CS) offers a solution by enabling signal acquisition with significantly fewer samples than the traditional Nyquist rate, thus conserving power at the sensing node. This technology is particularly beneficial in mobile healthcare to improve efficiency. Electrocardiogram (ECG) signals, essential for diagnosing heart diseases, pose challenges due to their need for continuous monitoring which is time-consuming and demands substantial power and bandwidth for signal transmission and reconstruction. Although various sensing strategies and reconstruction algorithms in CS for ECG signals have been explored, finding the optimal approach that ensures high accuracy at a higher compression ratio remains an unresolved issue. This research conducts a comprehensive analysis of six sensing strategies, namely Random Gaussian Matrix, Sparse Binary Matrix with 10% and 20% densities, Random Bernoulli Matrix with Signed Indices, Regular Low-Density Parity Check Matrix, and Structured Fourier Matrix, alongside Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and Wavelet (dB2) sparse bases. Additionally, we examine nine reconstruction algorithms: L1 Minimization, Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP), Compressive Sampling Matching Pursuit (CoSaMP), Iterative Soft Thresholding Algorithm (ISTA), Fast Iterative Soft Thresholding Algorithm (FISTA), Iterative Hard Thresholding (IHT), Iterative Reweighted Least Squares (IRLS), and Sparse Pursuit (SP). We aim to identify the most efficient method for ECG signal processing within the CS framework.

Index Terms—Compressive Sensing, IoMT, ECG, Healthcare, Compressed Sampling, Big Data.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) has become an integral part of modern healthcare, providing an interconnected environment where medical devices and applications

exchange data to facilitate real-time monitoring and diagnostics [1], [2]. As the IoMT continues to expand, so does the volume of data generated by medical devices, particularly those used for continuous health monitoring such as ECG signal monitoring [3]. Continuous monitoring of ECG signals is crucial for identifying different cardiac abnormalities, such as arrhythmias [4]. Such monitoring devices require substantial computational power for data processing, significant storage capacity, extensive bandwidth for data transmission, and increased power consumption [5]. The management of such extensive data not only challenges existing infrastructure but also raises concerns about efficiency and sustainability in healthcare technologies.

CS presents a transformative approach to data acquisition, particularly within the IoMT framework. By enabling the acquisition of signals at rates significantly below the Nyquist rate, CS reduces the need for extensive data transmission and storage, thereby conserving power and bandwidth [6]. The CS approach is particularly pertinent in healthcare, where devices like ECG monitors are essential yet consume considerable resources due to continuous data transmission [7]. Exploring compression techniques can help extend the lifetime of wearable sensors. CS proves to be an efficient compression method, offering high-quality reconstruction, and security while wireless data transmission and lower power consumption than traditional compression methods like transform coding and segmentation and labeling techniques [8], [9]. The emergence of CS has sparked numerous studies in connected health applications, exploiting the sparse nature of physiological signals. [10]–[12].

Furthermore, the literature contains numerous discussions on CS-based ECG monitoring platforms' design, implementation, and analysis. An initial comparative study of various compressed sensing reconstruction algorithms for ECG signals was conducted in [13] but they only analyzed the greedy and convex type algorithms. Additionally, Polania et al [14] introduced enhancements to two CS recovery algorithms for ECG signals, specifically iterative hard thresholding (IHT) and

compressive sampling matching pursuit (CoSAMP). These enhancements involve using prior knowledge of the signal's structure to improve the quality of the reconstruction [14]. The authors in [15] introduce an accelerated iterative shrinkage-thresholding algorithm called AFISTA. The core concept behind AFISTA is to enhance the convergence speed of the traditional FISTA by implementing a novel continuation strategy. This approach significantly reduces the number of iterations required compared to FISTA. Authors in [16] performed CS reconstruction called convex L1 optimization offline but it has not been compared with other algorithms to find the better. In [7], the researchers demonstrated real-time reconstruction of ECG signals on an iPhone using an adapted version of the iterative shrinkage-thresholding algorithm (ISTA). However, they did not address the trade-offs among execution time, power consumption, computational resource allocation, and signal dimensions. Additionally, research has been carried out on individual CS sensing matrices such as Random Gaussian Matrix (RGM) [17], Random Sparse Binary Matrix [14], Structured Fourier Sensing Matrix [18]. To successfully compress and recover the input signal with CS, it should have a sparse representation in a domain i.e., time domain, wavelet domain. For instance, the authors in [14] used wavelet sparse bases and Discrete Cosine Transform by [19] to find the sparse solution to the ECG signals. Additionally, there is also continuous development of CS reconstruction algorithms, sparse domains, and sensing matrices to reduce error rates or address special applications in remote monitoring.

In light of the aforementioned works, this article presents a comprehensive comparative study of nine leading state-of-the-art CS reconstruction algorithms, six sensing matrices, and two sparse bases. It aims to provide insight into approaches, functionality, and performance trade-offs. Furthermore, the experimental work is performed on PhysioNet databases, including the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [20], [21] sampled with aforementioned sensing matrices and then reconstructed using these algorithms.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II explains the CS for ECG signals; Section III describes the proposed methodology; Section IV presents the results and discussion; and Section V concludes the paper.

II. COMPRESSED SENSING FOR ECG SIGNALS

CS is based on the concept that a signal can be effectively represented using a smaller number of significant basis functions [6]. If a signal is primarily characterized by a few key basis functions, it is considered sparse. Imagine an input signal vector x with length N . This vector can be depicted as a linear combination of a set of basis functions in a particular domain, multiplied by a vector of sparse coefficients s , as shown in Equation (1).

$$x = \Psi s \quad (1)$$

Here, Ψ denotes an $N \times N$ basis function matrix, and s is an $N \times 1$ vector of sparse coefficients. The sparsity of x is

quantified by the number of significant non-zero coefficients in s . If x possesses only K non-zero coefficients in s , it is classified as K -sparse [22].

In the realm of CS, the sparse signal x is correlated with a set of measurement functions represented by an $M \times N$ measurement matrix Φ . The number of measurements is denoted by M , and the length of each measurement function is N . This correlation process is described in Equation (2).

$$y = \Phi x = \Phi \Psi s = A s \quad (2)$$

In this equation, y represents the compressed version of x , Φ is the measurement matrix that exhibits incoherence with the basis matrix Ψ , and A is defined as the reconstruction matrix. Given $K < M \ll N$, the compressed measurement vector y , which has a size of $M \times 1$, encapsulates adequate information for the accurate reconstruction of x [23].

III. METHODOLOGY

In this research, we apply CS to ECG Signals to find the suitable sensing matrix, sparse basis, and reconstruction algorithms. Our methodology comprises the following stage and is shown in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1. Proposed Methodology

Signal Representation: In CS, accurate reconstruction of ECG signals requires them to be sparse in either the time domain or a specific transform domain. However, ECG signals are not inherently sparse in the time domain. Therefore, we opt for the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and Wavelet (dB2) transforms as the sparse domains, as demonstrated in Eq. 1 and Fig. 1.

Sampling Process: We utilize the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database for ECG signals x sampled using $M \times N$ measurement matrix Φ , which includes Random Gaussian Matrix (RGM), Random Binary Matrix (RBMB) with densities of 10% and 20%, Random Bernoulli Matrix Signed (RBMS), Regular Low-Density Parity Check (RLDPC), and Structured Fourier Matrix (SFM). These matrices are selected for their incoherence with the basis matrix Ψ . The measurements y are obtained through this process, with the number of measurements M chosen based on compression ratios (CR) ranging from 10% to 90%.

Reconstruction Process: Using the compressed measurements y , we reconstruct the original ECG signal \hat{x} by employing the before-mentioned optimization algorithms aimed at minimizing the Percentage RMS Difference (PRD) error and maximizing the correlation coefficient (CC).

Evaluation Metrics: Each reconstruction algorithm’s performance is assessed based on the fidelity of the reconstructed signal $\hat{x} = \Psi\hat{s}$ relative to the original signal x . Key metrics include PRD, CC, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), and Reconstruction Time.

Experimental Setup: Initially, the acquired ECG signals were pre-processed to remove noise and artifacts. They were then transformed into the DCT and dB2 sparse domains to verify their sparsity. The entire CS framework was implemented on a computer running MATLAB 2023b, equipped with an Intel Core i7-13700HX CPU, 16GB of RAM, and Windows 11 operating system. Statistical analyses were conducted to compare the effectiveness of various combinations of sensing matrices, sparse bases, and reconstruction algorithms.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to Zigei et al. [24], cardiologists classify the quality of reconstructed ECG signals as follows: “very good” for a PRD between 0% and 2%, “good” for a PRD between 2% and 9%, “not good” for a PRD between 9% and 19%, and “bad” for a PRD between 19% and 60%. The effectiveness of a reconstruction algorithm depends on several factors, including the choice of measurement matrix, the number of measurements, the selection of sparse bases, the degree of incoherence between the sparse bases and measurement matrices, and the specific reconstruction algorithms used. In this study, we deeply analyzed the performance evaluations of the CS sensing matrices, sparse basis, and reconstruction algorithms by evaluating the PRD, CC, SNR, and complexity level analyzed using reconstruction time at different CRs ranging from 10% to 90%.

A. Wavelet Sparse Basis

Fig. 2 shows the CRs vs PRD trends of nine reconstruction algorithms for six sensing matrices. Across all plots, the dashed horizontal line represents a PRD threshold that cardiologists consider acceptable for diagnostic purposes. The relationship between PRD and CR across these matrices shows that while some matrices maintain lower PRDs at higher CRs indicating better performance, others do not perform as well, with PRD increasing rapidly as more compression is applied.

Sparse Binary Matrix (d=10%): The PRD remains relatively low and stable for lower CRs and begins to increase steadily after around a 50% CR, before sharply rising close to 90%. This indicates that up to a 50% CR, the reconstruction quality is largely preserved.

Sparse Binary Matrix (d=20%): This plot shows a trend similar to the Sparse Binary Matrix at 10% density, with PRD values that start to significantly increase past a 60% CR, suggesting slightly better sparsity tolerance due to higher density.

Random Bernoulli Matrix (Signed): The PRD trends upward gradually with increased CRs, with a more noticeable rise after 70% compression, suggesting moderate effectiveness in preserving signal integrity at higher compression levels.

Random Gaussian Matrix: Here, PRD starts to rise more significantly after 40% compression, indicating that this sensing matrix may not maintain signal quality as effectively at higher CRs compared to some other matrices.

Regular LDPC Matrix: The PRD for this matrix shows a consistent increase as the CR grows, but with a steeper climb after 50% compression, similar to the first Sparse Binary Matrix plot.

Structured Fourier Matrix: The performance here is notably different. The PRD values are generally higher across all CRs, showing a consistent and gradual increase. This suggests that while the Structured Fourier Matrix can compress the signal, it may not be as effective in preserving signal quality as the other matrices.

Additional parameters such as the CC, SNR, and reconstruction time were also evaluated. For the sake of brevity, not all diagrams could be included; therefore, we concentrated our analysis on the algorithms that deliver the lowest PRD at each CR. The corresponding values for CC, SNR, and Reconstruction Time are provided in Table I. The results demonstrate that the RL1 algorithm performs exceptionally well from CRs of 10% to 70% for RBMB, RBMS, RGM, and RLDPC matrices. FISTA and ISTA show very good performance at CRs of 80-90% for RBMB (d=10%) and RGM. The IRLS algorithm provides a lower PRD at a 90% compression ratio for RBMB (d=20%) and RBMS. For the RLDPC matrix, CVXL1 and FISTA offer the lowest PRD at compression ratios of 80% and 90%, respectively. Furthermore, CVXL1 demonstrates outstanding performance across all compression ratios for the Structured Fourier Matrix (SFM).

Fig. 2. Wavelet (dB2): PRD vs CR trends for different sensing matrices

B. Discrete Cosine Transform

Fig. 3 shows the same trends. The relationship between PRD and CR across these matrices for DCT shows that while some matrices maintain lower PRDs at higher compression ratios indicating better performance, others do not perform as well, with PRD increasing rapidly as more compression is applied.

Sparse Binary Matrix with d=10% and 20%): For both matrices, the PRD increases with the CR, indicating a

direct relationship. At lower compression ratios, the PRD is lower, suggesting that the reconstructed signal is closer to the original. However, as the compression ratio increases, the quality of reconstruction decreases, reflected by higher PRD values for all reconstruction algorithms. RBMB(d=20%) shows slightly lower PRD values for all CR as compared to RBMB(d=10%).

Random Gaussian Matrix: This matrix also shows a direct relationship between PRD and CR. However, the PRD values appear to increase more gradually compared to the sparse binary matrix, suggesting that the Random Gaussian Matrix may be more robust to compression.

Regular LDPC Matrix: There is a consistent increase in PRD with the CR. The slope of the PRD increase appears similar to that of the RGM, which suggests that the quality of the reconstruction degrades at a similar rate as compression increases.

Random Bernoulli Matrix (Signed): This also provides the same relationship to RLDPC. The PRD values seem to start lower but eventually rise steeply, indicating that initial reconstructions are good, but the quality degrades significantly at higher CRs.

Structured Fourier Matrix: The relationship here is slightly different; at lower CRs, the PRD is relatively high but does not increase as steeply with the CR. This suggests that while the initial reconstruction quality is not as good, it does not degrade as drastically with increased compression. It is important to note that CVXL1 shows constant PRD to 50% compression then sharply increases onwards. Analogous to wavelet analysis, other performance metrics have also been evaluated for the DCT. As presented in Table ??, the RL1 algorithm demonstrates exceptional performance at a 10% CR across all sensing matrices and achieves 90% at RBMS. Conversely, the IRLS algorithm yields lower PRD values and higher CC values for CRs ranging from 20% to 80% for all sensing matrices. Additionally, it exhibits commendable performance at 90% compression for RBMB, with d-values of 10% and 20%. Moreover, CVXL1 outperforms others at a 90% compression level for RGM, RLDPC, and SFM matrices. Our findings suggest that utilizing a CR greater than 10% may not be advisable, as it typically results in exceeding the PRD threshold, as supported by Zigel et al. [24]. Nonetheless, it is important to acknowledge the observed positive trend in CC, which signifies a strong correlation even at elevated CR levels. This indicates the efficiency of the DCT sparse basis in applications where CC is prioritized over PRD.

Furthermore, our analysis identifies a significant trade-off between the increasing CR and its impact on performance evaluation parameters. As the CR increases, there is a general decline in the CC, SNR, and computational time, while the PRD rises. This inverse relationship highlights the challenges in balancing compression efficiency with signal integrity. Notably, wavelet transforms (specifically, Daubechies 2 (dB2)) consistently outperform DCT across all sensing matrices and reconstruction algorithms. This suggests that wavelet-

Fig. 3. DCT: PRD vs CR trends for different sensing matrices

based sparse representations offer superior performance in maintaining signal fidelity, particularly in scenarios where higher compression ratios are required. The application of CS to the IoMT further highlights the critical importance of selecting the appropriate sensing matrix, sparse basis, and reconstruction algorithm. This selection is essential to achieve an optimal balance between power efficiency, computational complexity, and diagnostic accuracy. Despite the development of various CS frameworks documented in the literature, the quest to identify the most effective framework continues. Our comprehensive study involving six different sensing matrices, two types of sparse bases, and nine reconstruction algorithms, reveals that while all tested sensing matrices provide a commendable balance between accuracy and time complexity, the ease of implementation varies significantly as shown in Table I. Particularly, random matrices such as RGM, RBMB, and RBMS present challenges in hardware implementation due to their stochastic nature and the complexity involved in generating and storing random elements. Conversely, structured matrices like the RLDPC matrix are more suited to hardware implementations. Their structured nature facilitates easier integration into existing digital systems, making them a preferable choice for practical applications.

V. CONCLUSION

This study has explored the application of CS to ECG signals within the IoMT. We have investigated six distinct sensing matrices and two sparse bases, evaluating their performance across nine advanced reconstruction algorithms. Our findings demonstrate that Daubechies 2 (dB2) wavelets consistently provide superior preservation of ECG signal integrity over DCT, particularly at higher compression ratios. Among the sensing matrices, the Regular Low-Density Parity Check RLDPC have shown promising results, though with specific strengths and limitations. RLDPC matrices, due to their structured nature, are more conducive to hardware implementation. In terms of reconstruction algorithms IRL1 have proven effective with db2 and IRLS with DCT across a variety of scenarios, suggesting their robustness and adaptability to different types of sensing matrices and compression ratios.

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ALL SENSING MATRICES, RECONSTRUCTION
ALGORITHMS AND SPARSE BASIS

Sparse Wavelet Basis (dB2)						Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT)					
CR	PRD	Algo.	CC	SNR	Time	PRD	Algo.	CC	SNR	Time	
Sparse Binary Matrix (10%)											
10	1.559	IRLS	0.999	36.190	1.371	7.609	RL1	0.987	22.507	10.254	
20	2.410	RL1	0.999	32.682	9.597	13.569	IRLS	0.957	17.472	1.071	
30	3.365	RL1	0.997	29.436	7.535	18.831	IRLS	0.915	14.576	0.703	
40	4.807	RL1	0.994	26.128	6.452	24.928	IRLS	0.847	12.129	0.496	
50	9.140	RL1	0.983	21.517	5.173	31.027	IRLS	0.754	10.206	0.352	
60	13.705	RL1	0.948	16.721	3.774	35.298	IRLS	0.665	9.092	0.177	
70	23.009	RL1	0.832	11.854	3.155	39.989	IRLS	0.545	8.005	0.101	
80	34.813	FISTA	0.622	9.243	0.024	42.327	IRLS	0.446	7.494	0.050	
90	48.176	FISTA	0.250	6.407	0.016	44.964	IRLS	0.305	6.968	0.019	
Sparse Binary Matrix (20%)											
10	1.492	RL1	0.999	36.583	10.675	7.543	RL1	0.987	22.582	10.434	
20	2.403	RL1	0.999	32.438	9.870	13.672	IRLS	0.956	17.406	1.053	
30	3.402	RL1	0.997	29.416	7.606	19.680	IRLS	0.908	14.179	0.708	
40	4.909	RL1	0.995	26.244	6.576	24.903	IRLS	0.847	12.127	0.498	
50	8.101	RL1	0.985	21.959	5.262	30.789	IRLS	0.758	10.273	0.355	
60	14.909	RL1	0.948	16.634	3.850	35.561	IRLS	0.659	9.025	0.181	
70	25.163	RL1	0.845	12.115	3.206	39.566	IRLS	0.556	8.095	0.110	
80	37.366	FISTA	0.613	8.639	0.031	42.762	IRLS	0.430	7.405	0.054	
90	48.053	IRLS	0.235	6.390	0.018	44.733	IRLS	0.318	7.012	0.020	
Random Bernoulli Matrix (Signed)											
10	1.558	RL1	0.999	36.205	10.897	7.280	RL1	0.988	22.926	10.378	
20	2.349	RL1	0.999	32.641	9.812	13.556	IRLS	0.957	17.464	1.031	
30	3.476	RL1	0.997	29.245	7.474	19.868	IRLS	0.906	14.114	0.687	
40	5.005	RL1	0.994	26.085	6.457	25.456	IRLS	0.841	11.947	0.491	
50	8.182	RL1	0.985	21.859	5.228	30.088	IRLS	0.772	10.490	0.349	
60	15.888	RL1	0.941	16.135	3.828	35.524	IRLS	0.667	9.029	0.178	
70	26.047	RL1	0.839	11.797	3.229	40.788	IRLS	0.538	7.825	0.102	
80	41.682	RL1	0.380	4.417	2.531	43.191	IRLS	0.440	7.315	0.049	
90	90.661	IRLS	0.150	0.853	0.026	57.454	RL1	0.152	4.862	2.188	
Random Gaussian Matrix											
10	1.590	RL1	0.999	36.037	10.627	7.391	RL1	0.987	22.752	10.289	
20	2.306	RL1	0.999	32.792	9.610	13.624	IRLS	0.957	17.424	1.039	
30	3.297	RL1	0.998	29.677	7.539	19.725	IRLS	0.907	14.187	0.714	
40	5.139	RL1	0.994	25.858	6.412	25.242	IRLS	0.844	12.019	0.497	
50	8.381	RL1	0.984	21.700	5.254	30.961	IRLS	0.758	10.234	0.352	
60	15.701	RL1	0.943	16.202	3.738	35.420	IRLS	0.669	9.062	0.183	
70	28.285	RL1	0.812	11.119	3.201	40.206	IRLS	0.557	7.948	0.107	
80	43.605	ISTA	0.491	6.879	0.019	44.308	IRLS	0.447	7.106	0.050	
90	48.594	ISTA	0.361	6.548	0.014	53.488	CVXL1	0.179	5.469	0.573	
Regular LDPC Matrix											
10	1.545	RL1	0.999	36.283	10.840	7.391	RL1	0.988	22.960	10.712	
20	2.398	RL1	0.999	32.456	9.719	13.624	IRLS	0.957	17.506	1.061	
30	3.385	RL1	0.997	29.474	7.680	19.725	IRLS	0.911	14.347	0.730	
40	4.957	RL1	0.994	26.164	6.377	25.242	IRLS	0.839	11.959	0.509	
50	7.944	RL1	0.986	22.101	5.279	30.961	IRLS	0.766	10.420	0.359	
60	15.187	RL1	0.946	16.496	3.690	35.420	IRLS	0.664	9.077	0.186	
70	24.479	RL1	0.853	12.320	3.238	40.206	IRLS	0.556	8.072	0.115	
80	38.462	CVXL1	0.603	8.380	0.491	44.308	IRLS	0.443	7.479	0.055	
90	44.600	FISTA	0.453	5.343	0.161	53.488	CVXL1	0.187	5.886	0.558	
Structured Fourier Matrix											
10	1.127	CVXL1	0.997	18.531	4.511	7.391	RL1	0.902	14.069	25.122	
20	1.111	CVXL1	0.991	17.374	3.595	13.624	IRLS	0.839	11.277	3.181	
30	1.100	CVXL1	0.981	17.560	2.560	19.725	IRLS	0.846	11.004	2.288	
40	1.460	CVXL1	0.970	17.024	2.017	25.242	IRLS	0.858	11.103	1.603	
50	2.689	CVXL1	0.960	10.180	1.595	30.961	IRLS	0.875	11.249	1.136	
60	4.040	CVXL1	0.950	8.151	1.463	35.420	IRLS	0.884	11.356	0.668	
70	10.219	CVXL1	0.949	8.952	1.107	40.206	IRLS	0.874	11.175	0.373	
80	15.752	CVXL1	0.944	7.132	0.744	44.308	IRLS	0.858	10.737	0.158	
90	33.174	CVXL1	0.711	6.645	0.564	53.488	CVXL1	0.705	9.547	0.559	

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